

Development of Antimicrobial Textiles using Neem Seed Extract - A Sustainable Approach

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Abstract;

*This study focused on the extraction of natural antimicrobial agent from neem seed (*Azadirachta indica*) to apply it on cotton, polyester and linen fabrics. Aqueous neem-seed extract had been prepared by decoction method and major compounds were identified by phytochemical analysis. The neem seed extract of optimized concentration with cross-linking agent was applied on to fabrics by pad-dry-cure method. The finished fabrics were analyzed for antimicrobial activity against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. The results show that the neem treated linen fabric has the best antimicrobial activity when compared to neem-treated cotton and polyester fabrics. FTIR spectrum of the treated fabric samples confirmed the presence of bioactive compounds in the finished fabric. The study suggests that neem seed extract could be a less expensive, non-toxic and effective alternative to traditional antimicrobial agents for fabric treatment.*

Keywords: *antimicrobial agent, cotton, decoction method, linen, neem seed extract, phytochemical analysis, polyester*

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1. Introduction

Antimicrobial textiles are gaining popularity due to the increasing demand for products that offer protection against bacteria and other microorganisms. The use of natural antimicrobial agents in the textile industry is a sustainable approach that can offer an eco-friendly alternative to traditional chemical-based treatments. The antibacterial properties of Neem oil in combination with other herbal oils such as Clove, Tulsi and Karanga have been used to impart antimicrobial finish on cotton textiles.

Neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*) is one of the richest sources of bioactive compounds, belongs to the Meliaceae (Mahogany) family and is abundantly found in the Indian subcontinent. Neem leaf extract is widely used by Indian farmers to protect the crop from pests and fungi which has potential antibacterial properties. Earlier studies reveal that neem seed or bark extract with a crosslinking agent was applied on to cotton fabric by conventional or microwave-curing methods [1]. The use of natural products for imparting antibacterial properties to textiles is gaining importance due to concerns over the environmental impact and potential health hazards associated with synthetic chemical. Attempts are being made to develop effective and long lasting antimicrobial finishes on textiles as textiles can harbor harmful bacteria causing skin infections and other illnesses [2, 3].

The traditional chemical treatments can have negative environmental impacts and may not be suitable for certain applications and thus making natural extracts as a promising alternative. Many studies reported the effectiveness of plant extracts in preventing bacterial growth on fabrics [4]. It was claimed that the bioactive constituents in neem are less toxic to warm-blooded animals like human [5]. In the recent years, neem extract has gained attention for its potential use in textile applications due to its antimicrobial, antiviral, and antifungal properties [6-8].

The natural fabric treated with neem, combined with citric acid, exhibits superior antimicrobial activity compared to the fabric treated with acetic acid. Increasing the concentration of the neem leaf extracted solution enhances the effectiveness of the antimicrobial activity on the cotton fabric. Among the various concentrations of the extracted solution, the treatment using a 7g/l concentration, along with citric acid, yields the highest level of antimicrobial activity on the treated natural fabric [9]. Earlier studies disclose the use of neem for the functional finishing of textile materials [10, 11]. Phytochemical analysis is used to identify and quantify the chemical compounds in plants, providing insights into their medicinal and nutritional value, and guiding the development of drugs and natural products. Neem leaf extracts contain organic compounds like nimbidin, nimbolide, mahmoodin, margolone, margolonone, and isomargolonon, all of which show good antibiotic properties [12]. A study on antimicrobial effectiveness of flax demonstrates excellent zone of inhibition against the gram positive (*S. pyogenes*) and gram negative (*K. aerogenes*) bacteria around the treated fabric [13]. Neem essential oil nanoparticles were formulated using nano-emulsion and ionic gelation technique and applied to cotton and polyester fabric to give them antibacterial properties [14].

2. Materials and Methods

The woven textile materials selected for the study included 100% cotton, 100% polyester and 100% linen fabrics. The natural and synthetic fibre based fabrics chosen for the study find many textile applications including but not limited to clothing, home textiles and upholstery. The specifications of fabrics sourced from local markets.

The active ingredient used in the antimicrobial finishing is the kernel with the coat of the neem seed. It has already been well documented that the extract of the neem seeds has antimicrobial properties. In addition, neem extract is also known to repel insects, making it a popular natural insecticide.

2.1 Preparation of Neem Seed Extract

The fresh neem seeds were obtained by squeezing out the skin of the neem fruits collected from neem trees of southern India. Neem seeds were washed thoroughly two to three times with distilled water. Then the seeds were shadow dried at room temperature (~30°C) for five to seven days. After complete drying, the seeds were crushed into a coarse powder by using the grinder.

Figure 1 - Neem seed Powder

The active compounds from dried neem seed were extracted by one of the aqueous extraction methods stated elsewhere (Decoction Method). The extract was then cooled and filtered through the whatman no1 filter paper. The filtered extract was further analysed to identify the bioactive compounds present.

2.2 Phytochemical Testing of Aqueous Neem Seed Extract

Qualitative phytochemical tests were performed to identify the bioactive compounds present in the neem seed extract. The analysis confirmed the presence of Azadirachtin, the major active component along with other compounds like Nimbolinin, Nimbin, Teraponids, and Tannins etc.

Analyzing plant extracts to spot and describe the presence of different bioactive compounds is known as phytochemical screening. These substances, also referred to as phytochemicals, are essential to plants' metabolic and defense mechanisms. Phytochemical screening of plant extracts revealed the presence of terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins etc. [12]. The presence of such phytochemicals protects the plant from harmful agents such as insects and microbes as well as a stressful event such as ultraviolet (UV) irradiation and extreme temperature.

2.2.1 Flavonoids and testing

Flavonoids are referred to as Vitamin P. It is classified into iso-flavonoid and neo-flavonoid which are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. These are ketone-containing compounds and as such they are canthaxanthins (flavones and flavanols). It is the most important plant pigment. Flavonoids act as chemical messengers, physiological regulators and cell cycle inhibitors. Some clinical studies have suggested that flavonoids play a role in cancer prevention. It is said to have a direct antimicrobial activity.

Figure 2 - Structure of Iso-flavone

Figure 3 Structure of Neo Flavonoids

The aqueous extract of neem seed of 1 ml was taken in a test tube. The extract has a natural colour of yellow. Ethanol (95% conc.) of 1ml was added to the extract followed by adding few drops of 2% sodium hydroxide and dilute (20% conc.) hydrochloric acid. Gradually the yellow color of the solution disappeared and turns to milky white. This is an indication for the presence of flavonoid in the extract.

2.2.2 Terpenoids and Testing

It's also called isoprenoids which are naturally occurring organic chemicals similar to terpenes. Plant terpenoids are used for their aromatic qualities. They also have a role in herbal remedies. Azadirachtin is the terpenoid present in neem plant. The molecular structure of Azadirachtin is shown in Fig 4.

Figure 4 - Structure of Azadirachtin

The aqueous extract of neem seed of 1 ml which has a natural yellow colour was taken in a test tube. With continuous stirring, ethanol (95% conc.) of 1 ml was added in drops followed by adding few drops of chloroform and concentrated (98%) sulphuric acid. The solution gradually turns to reddish brown which is an indication for the presence of terpenoids.

2.2.3 Saponins and Testing

Saponins are amphipathic glycosides. When shaken in aqueous solutions it forms foams. In plants saponins serve as anti-feed to ants and also protect the plant against microbes and fungi. It may also enhance nutrient absorption and aid in animal digestion. Saponins are found to be toxic in cold-blooded organisms and insects at particular concentrations. Saponins are often bitter to taste and are easily dissolved in water.

The aqueous extract (1 ml) was taken in a test tube. Ethanol (95% conc.) of 1 ml was added to the extract and the test tube was shaken well. The reaction generates foam which is an indication for the presence of saponins.

2.2.4 Tannin and Testing

Tannin is an astringent, bitter plant polyphenolic compound which binds to and precipitates proteins and compounds like amino acids and alkaloids. It has a role in plant growth regulation, protection from predation and as a pesticide. Tannins are found in leaf, seed, and roots, stem tissues. Depending on the chemical structure and dosage tannins are considered anti-nutritional.

The extract solution (1 ml) was taken in a test tube. Ethanol (95% conc.) of 1 ml and 10% alcoholic ferric chloride were added to the solution. The reaction produced a brownish yellow color of the solution. This colour change validates the presence of tannins in the solution.

Figure 5 - Phytochemical test, A- Terpenoids, B- Flavonoids, C- Tannin, D- Saponins

2.3 Antibacterial Finishing of Fabrics

Pad-Dry-Cure method was adopted to apply the antimicrobial finish on fabrics. The laboratory model padding mangle was used for the study. The fabrics were first immersed in the decocted neem seed extract of concentration 7g/l for thirty minutes. Acetic acid was added to maintain the pH level of 5.5. Material to liquor ratio of the bath was maintained at 1:30. To achieve better wash fastness of the finish, citric acid of 10% w/w of fabric sample was also added to the bath as cross-linking agent. The fabric samples were then allowed to pass through the vertically arranged bowls of padding mangle to squeeze out excessive solution. All the fabric samples were then dried at 80° C for five minutes followed by curing at 120° C for three minutes in the curing chamber.

2.3.1 Antibacterial Test

Antibiotics represent a major class of antimicrobial agents. By definition, antibiotics are biochemicals produced by microorganisms that inhibit the growth of, or kill pathogenic microorganisms. The ISO 20645 agar diffusion test method was employed to qualitatively evaluate the antimicrobial properties of textile material. A clear zone of inhibition is formed around the test specimen if there is antibacterial activity.

2.4 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

Infrared spectroscopy is an important technique and an easy way to categorise the functional groups in a molecule. Also, one can use the unique collection of absorption bands to confirm the identity of a pure compound or to detect the presence of specific impurities. Analysis by infrared spectroscopy is based on the fact that molecules have specific frequencies of internal vibrations. These frequencies occur in the infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum over the spectrum range of 4000 cm⁻¹ to 200 cm⁻¹ [13].

3. Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the various tests conducted on treated and untreated fabric samples are discussed herein.

3.1 Heat and Time Effect of Extract Concentration

The decoction method of extraction of active ingredients involves heating the aqueous solution containing neem seed powder to boil. As the duration of heating increases, the concentration of extract also increases upto 20 minutes of heating and then stabilizes to a constant level. The decocted extract was visually examined and graded for concentration subjectively. The details are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Extract Concentration based on duration of heating

Sample No.	Heating time (minutes)	Concentration (subjective assessment)
1	5	Very low

2	10	Low
3	15	Average
4	20	High

The decocted extracts collected for visual examination are shown in Fig. 6. The four samples of the extract are shown in increasing order of concentration, sample 1 with low concentration obtained from minimal duration of heating and sample 4 is highly concentrated corresponding to maximum duration of heating.

Sample No	Heating time (minutes)	Concentration (subjective assessment)
1	5	Very low
2	10	Low
3	15	Average
4	20	High

Figure 6 - Decocted samples with varying concentration

3.2 Antimicrobial performance

The possible mechanism of antimicrobial activity is either by preventing microbial growth or potential cell wall breakdown of bacteria. All fabric samples treated with neem seed extract showed antibacterial activity against both gram positive (*S.Aureus*) and gram negative (*E-Coli*) bacteria. Fig.7 shows the effect of antimicrobial activity (zone of inhibition) of untreated and treated samples of three different fabrics. Referring to Fig.7 (a), treated linen sample exhibits the highest level of antimicrobial activity against *E-Coli* as seen from the larger zone of inhibition measuring 24 mm followed by cotton and polyester with 20 mm and 16 mm respectively. No antimicrobial activity is observed in all the untreated fabric samples. The larger zone of inhibition of linen fabric sample is attributed to the high lignin content of flax fibre since lignin is a natural antibacterial. Lignin content in its chemical composition causes products made of this fibre to efficiently protect the user from UV radiation [15]. Higher moisture content of flax also could help in leaching out of the active compounds resulting in a larger zone of inhibition. Low level of antimicrobial activity of polyester fabric is attributable to the absence of reactive groups for bond formation with the active factors of extract.

Figure 7 - Disk with fabric samples, (a) linen, (b) cotton and (c) polyester

3.3 FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) characteristics

FTIR spectroscopy was conducted on all treated and untreated fabric samples and shown in Fig.8, 9 and 10. Fig.8 is a comparison of treated and untreated cotton fabrics.

Figure 8 - FTIR Spectra of treated and untreated cotton fabric

As seen from Fig.8, some of the intense peaks are identical for both untreated and fabrics. The peak of 2336 cm⁻¹ corresponds to C=C stretch vibration of aromatic cellulose of cotton. Similarly the peaks at 1009 cm⁻¹ and 1038 cm⁻¹ due to C-H stretching and peaks of 1514 cm⁻¹ and 1526 cm⁻¹ of C-O stretching refers to cotton cellulose. The unique peak of treated fabric at 2916 cm⁻¹ corresponds to carboxylic acid O-H stretch and a peak at 1734 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of C=O (Esters, Carboxylic acids, Ketones, Aldehydes) which are the functional groups present in the active compounds of neem seed extract.

Figure 9 - FTIR Spectra of unfinished and finished linen fabric

From Fig.9, identical peaks are observed at wave numbers 3288, 3274, 1038, 1036, 548, 547 in both untreated and treated linen fabric which are functional groups present in the polymer structure of flax fibre. The unique peak at 2335 cm⁻¹ corresponds to N-H stretching of amines and amides present in the active principles of neem seed extract.

Figure 10 - FTIR Spectra of unfinished and finished Polyester fabric

The peaks in the IR spectra of treated and untreated polyester fabric are shown in Fig.10. The peak at 1709 cm⁻¹ shows C=O vibration which indicates the presence of ester group in the polymer of polyester. The other peaks of the spectra of polyester fabric might be the impurities present in the polymer structure. No specific difference

between the spectra of treated and untreated samples could be traced. Unlike cotton and linen, polyester has no reactive groups like OH and there is no likely formation of hydrogen bonds with bioactive compounds.

4. Conclusion and Scope

The study reveals that bioactive compounds are present in aqueous seed extract obtained by decoction method as tested by qualitative phytochemical analysis. Azadiractin is a major constituent of tannins which is an effective antimicrobial agent. Decoction method is a simple and easy process of extracting bioactive compounds from plants, however, at elevated temperatures it is likely that some of the compounds may be dissociated.

All fabric samples finished with aqueous neem seed extract exhibit antibacterial activity as seen from the zone of inhibition. It is observed that among three fabric samples of linen, cotton and polyester, the linen fabric showed larger zone of inhibition which could be attributed to the higher lignin content of flax fibre. FTIR spectra of finished fabric samples establish the constituent functional groups of bioactive compounds present in the neem seed extract as well as the polymer composition of fibres.

Selective use of bioactive compounds of plant extracts is a sustainable way for textile finishing. Plant varieties are renewable and also abundantly available thus cost effective methods can be devised for various types of textile finishes. Neem based textile materials seems to be promising alternative to chemically synthesized finishing agents. Neem treated textile materials have the potential to replace the traditional materials used in home textiles, healthcare and hygiene textiles.

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